

29%; CAR5, 19%, and CAR6, 23%, over check Toul Samrong 2.

The new varieties are photoperiod-sensitive. They can be sown between May and August and still flower at a given range of time. CAR1, CAR2, and CAR3 are medium-duration varieties. CAR1 and CAR3 can flower as early as the first week of November while CAR2 can flower as early as the third

week of October (Table 2). CAR4, CAR5, and CAR6 are late-duration varieties. They can flower as early as the second week of November. Their mean growth duration is about a week longer than that of CAR1, CAR2, and CAR3. In general, they are taller than the medium-duration varieties.

A sensory test using 94 evaluators showed that the raw and cooked rice

qualities of the six varieties were acceptable. The raw milled rice acceptability for CAR3 was 75%. It was at least 90% for the other varieties. Cooked rice acceptability was 87% for CAR1 and CAR2 and more than 95% for the other varieties. All six varieties have medium-sized grains, with length-breadth ratio ranging from 2.49 for CAR3 to 2.99 for CAR4 and CAR6. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

FARO 45 to FARO 49: two early-maturing and three medium-maturing upland rice varieties released in Nigeria

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Upland rice is grown on 30% of the 1.77 million ha planted to rice in Nigeria. In August 1996, the National Crop Variety Release Committee released two early-maturing and three medium-maturing

upland rice varieties for different agroecological zones in Nigeria. Their characteristics are shown in the table.

FARO 45 is more suited to the northwestern and northeastern zones, while FARO 46 is recommended for all the five agroecological zones of the country. Both are harvested at around 100 d after seeding.

FARO 47 is recommended for the southeastern zone, and FARO 48 and FARO 49 are suitable for hydromorphic areas of the Niger, Benue, and Plateau states in central Nigeria and upland areas of southwestern Nigeria. These three varieties have durations of 115-120 d.

All varieties are ITA lines selected from the crosses made in IITA, Ibadan. FARO 45 is ITA 257 line, selected in F₄ generation from a three-way cross made in 1979. It involved parents such as IRAT 13, Dourado Precoce, LAC 23, IET1444, OS 6, CP-SLO, and TN1. FARO 46 is ITA 150 line, selected in F₅ from a single cross made in 1976. It involved parents such as 63-83, ROK 1, SE363G, and Dourado Precoce. FARO 47 is ITA 117 line, selected in F₅ from a cross made in 1975. It involved parents such as 13A, CP-SLO, TN1, and OS 6. FARO 48 is ITA301 line, selected in F₈ from a three-way cross among IRAT13, Dourado Precoce, and Padipayak

Agronomic characteristics of two early- and three medium-maturing upland rice varieties. Ibadan, Nigeria.

	FARO 45	FARO 46	FARO 47	FARO 48	FARO 49
Designation	ITA257	ITA150	ITA117	ITA301	ITA315
Line	TOX10114-1	TOX502-41-1-1	TOX356-1-1-1	TOX854-101-3-201-1-1-1	TOX936-397-9-1-2
Cross	IRAT13/Dourado Precoce/TOX490-1	63-83/Multiple parent#23 ^b	13A218-3-1-3/ 1529-430-3/ TOX7-4-2-5-2	IRAT13/Dourado Precoce// Padipayak	IR1529-430-3/ Iguape Cateto
Year of hybridization	1979	1975	1975	1978	1979
Plant height (cm)	100	110	105	100	100
Days to 50% flowering	70	75	85	98	90
Blast resistance ^a	1	1	1	1	1
Drought tolerance ^a	1	1	3	1	1
Leaf scald ^a	3	1	1	5	7
Brown rice length (mm)	6.5	7.5	7.2	7.4	7.0
Brown rice width (mm)	2.9	2.6	2.2	2.4	2.7
Brown rice L/W	2.2	2.9	3.1	3.1	2.6
Brown rice shape	Medium bold	Long bold	Long slender	Long slender	Long bold
Chalkiness ^a	1	1	1	5	9
Gelatinization temperature ^a	3	5	5	5	3
Gel consistency ^a	3	5	5	5	1
Amylose(%)	17.4	22.5	19.5	16.4	16.2
Husk color	Golden	Golden	Straw	Straw	Straw
1000 grain weight (g)	31.0	33.5	26.5	29.5	30.5
Av grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	2.0	2.0	2.5	2.5	2.0
Yield potential (t ha ⁻¹)	3.5	3.0	3.5	3.5	3.5

^aSES scale (IRRI 1996). ^bMultiple parent #23: ROK1, SE 363G, and Dourado Precoce.

made in 1978. FARO 49 is ITA315 line, selected in F₆ from a single cross made in 1979. It involved parents such as Sigadis, TN1, Peta, Dee-geo-woo-gen, CP-SLO, and Iguape Cateto.

All five varieties are resistant to leaf blast. FARO 45 and FARO 46 are resistant to leaf scald. These are the

major problems affecting upland rice in Nigeria. FARO 45 and FARO 46 also have drought tolerance and escape drought damage because they mature early.

The lines were evaluated in multi-locational coordinated rice evaluation trials (CRET) in Nigeria. After 3 yr of

superior performances in these trials, they were evaluated in farmers' fields. The varieties are location-specific. FARO 45 is not suited for the acidic uplands of the humid forest zone. The WARDA Lowland Rice Breeding Unit at IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria, is producing breeder seed of all varieties. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—flood-prone

Saraswati and Jalaprabha: two new deepwater rice varieties for eastern India

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The State Variety Release Committee, West Bengal, approved the release of two varieties, Saraswati (CN584-311-10) and Jalaprabha for deepwater ecosystems (50-100 cm) in June 1996. Saraswati is a pedigree selection from the cross Pankaj/Patnai 23, done at RRS. It was evaluated as IET11271 in national trials during 1989-94 (Table 1). The pooled average yield across 36 locations was 50% more than national check Utkal Prabha. In national testing, it ranked fourth in the 1989 preliminary variety trial, eighth in the 1993 advanced variety trial-semideep water, and second in the 1994 advanced variety trial-semideep water, tested over 13 locations. The variety's mean yield was 2.7 t ha⁻¹ with yield potential of 4.6 t ha⁻¹. The All-India Rice Workshop suggested it for use in the deepwater areas of Assam, West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, and Orissa.

Saraswati is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and flowers around the end of October. Its submergence tolerance is mainly through elongation, and it has very good kneeing ability. Panicles are well exerted with short, bold golden grains and purple apiculi. Kernels are about 5.5 × 2.6 mm. Hulling percentage is 78.5 and milling percentage is 68.5.

Table 1. Performance of Saraswati in national trials in India. 1989-94.

Year	Trial ^a /site	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Maximum water depth (cm)
		Saraswati	Utkal Prabha	
1989	PVT5			
	Patna, Bihar	4.5 ^b	2.1	65
	Pusa, Bihar	4.6	3.7	55
	Karimganj, Assam	2.6	2.4	25
	Pulla, Andhra Pradesh	4.3	2.6	80
1990	IVT-SDW			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.8 ^b	Nil	70
	Sabour, Bihar	3.7	3.2	na ^c
	Ghagraghat, Uttar Pradesh	2.0 ^b	1.2	na
	Canning, West Bengal	4.2 ^b	Nil	na
	North Lakhimpur, Assam	3.5	3.3	na
1991	AVT-SDW			
	Ranital, Orissa	2.1 ^a	1.8	na
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	3.6 ^b	2.3	65
	Karimganj, Assam	3.2	2.3	na
	Patna, Bihar	1.9	1.5	na
	Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh	1.1	0.5	na
	Ghagraghat, Uttar Pradesh	2.0	1.3	na
1992	AVT-SDW			
	Pulla, Andhra Pradesh	1.5	1.4	60
	CRR1, Orissa	1.7	1.4	100
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.2 ^b	0.2	55
	Sabour, Bihar	2.4	2.4	45
	Karimganj, Assam	4.1 ^b	3.5	25
1993	AVT-SDW			
	CRR1, Orissa	1.6 ^b	0.7	na
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	4.1 ^b	1.6	75
	Patna, Bihar	2.9	2.2	na
	Pusa, Bihar	1.10	Nil	75
	Sabour, Bihar	2.7 ^b	1.9	na
	Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh	3.1 ^b	2.3	30
	Karimganj, Assam	3.9	3.8	31
1994	AVT-SDW			
	Ranital, Orissa	2.5 ^b	1.3	50
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	2.5 ^b	1.1	50
	Gosaba, West Bengal	3.5	2.9	50
	Patna, Bihar	1.7	1.5	na
	Sabour, Bihar	2.3 ^b	0.7	na
	Masodha, Uttar Pradesh	3.2 ^b	1.8	60
	Ghagraghat, Uttar Pradesh	1.7	1.5	50
	Canning, West Bengal	2.9	2.6	na
	Karimganj, Assam	2.6 ^b	2.1	na

^a PVT 5 = preliminary variety trial 5, IVT-SDW = initial variety trial-semideepwater, AVT-SDW = advanced variety trial-semideepwater.

^b Significantly superior to national check at the 5% level. ^c na = not available.